

Cadaveric Study of Anatomical Variations of Renal Arteries

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Abstract:

Background: Understanding the anatomical variations of renal arteries is crucial for preventing complications during renal transplant surgeries, angiographic procedures, and other renal interventions.

Aim: This study aims to document and analyze the variations in the renal arteries observed in human cadavers.

Methods: This cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Department of Anatomy, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College, Gaya.. Eighty-three cadavers (166 kidneys) were included based on intact renal systems and exclusion of those with prior renal surgeries or significant postmortem deterioration. Renal arteries were dissected and traced from their origin at the abdominal aorta to their entry points into the kidneys. Data were collected on the number, origin, and entry points of the renal arteries. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0, employing descriptive statistics and Chi-square tests to compare variations by laterality and sex, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The study found that anatomical variations in renal arteries occurred in 62.65% of cadavers, with accessory renal arteries being the most common variation (28.92%). Variations were more frequent on the right side (34.93%) compared to the left (25.30%), and there was no significant difference between male and female cadavers. These findings highlight the importance of recognizing renal artery variations in surgical planning to minimize complications.

Conclusion: Prior knowledge of renal artery variations is essential to prevent surgical and angiographic complications. The study underscores the importance of incorporating this knowledge into clinical practice to enhance the safety and efficiency of renal-related procedures.

Recommendations: Further research should continue to document these variations in different populations and settings to refine surgical techniques and improve patient outcomes. Clinicians should consider preoperative imaging to identify these variations before performing any renal interventions.

Keywords: Renal arteries, Accessory renal artery, Anatomical variations, Renal transplant, Surgical complications

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Introduction

Anatomical variations in the renal arteries are of significant clinical importance due to their implications in various medical and surgical procedures. The renal arteries, typically originating from the abdominal aorta, are primarily responsible for supplying blood to the kidneys. However, deviations from this standard anatomy, such as the presence of accessory renal arteries, are not uncommon and can pose challenges during interventions such as renal transplantation, endovascular procedures, and diagnostic angiography [1].

The variations in the renal arterial anatomy have been well-documented in medical literature. These variations can include differences in the number, origin, and branching patterns of the renal arteries. Understanding these variations is crucial for surgeons and radiologists to avoid intraoperative com-

plications and ensure the success of procedures involving the kidneys. For instance, the presence of accessory renal arteries can complicate the surgical field during a nephrectomy or renal transplantation, potentially leading to vascular injuries or inadequate perfusion of the renal tissue [2].

Given the critical role of renal arteries in maintaining kidney function and the potential complications arising from their anatomical variations, it is imperative to have a thorough understanding of these variations. The prevalence of accessory renal arteries have been highlighted by studies, yet there remains a need for continuous research to document these variations across different populations and improve clinical outcomes. Knowledge of these variations can guide preoperative planning and

surgical techniques, reducing the risk of postoperative complications [3].

The aim of this study is to document and analyze the anatomical variations of the renal arteries observed in human cadavers. By meticulously studying the origin, number, and entry points of these arteries, the research seeks to provide valuable data that can enhance the safety and efficacy of renal surgeries and interventions. This study also aims to compare the findings with existing literature to identify any patterns or significant deviations that may be specific to the studied population. Understanding the anatomical variations of the renal arteries is vital for clinicians involved in renal procedures. This study aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by providing detailed observations of renal artery variations in a cadaveric sample. The findings will have practical implications for improving surgical and diagnostic approaches, ultimately benefiting patient care in nephrology and urology.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a cross-sectional observational study aimed at documenting and analyzing the anatomical variations of renal arteries in human cadavers.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Department of Anatomy, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College, Gaya, over a period of one year from March 2020 to February 2021.

Participants: The study included 83 cadavers, providing a total of 166 kidneys for analysis. The cadavers were obtained from routine educational dissections conducted in the anatomy department.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Cadavers included in the study were those with intact renal systems and without any prior surgical alterations. Cadavers with significant postmortem deterioration, congenital anomalies unrelated to the renal arteries, or previous renal surgeries were excluded from the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all cadavers available during the study period that met the inclusion criteria were included. Observer bias was minimized by having multiple anatomists independently verify the findings.

Variables: The primary variables measured were the number of renal arteries, their points of origin from the abdominal aorta, and their entry points into the kidneys (hilum, upper pole, or lower pole).

Data Collection: Data were collected through direct observation and dissection of the renal arterial system in each cadaver. The origins and branching patterns of the renal arteries were documented, photographed, and recorded in a structured data sheet.

Procedure: Each cadaver was placed in a supine position, and a midline incision was made to expose the abdominal cavity. The posterior abdominal wall was dissected to reveal the kidneys and their arterial supply. The renal arteries were traced from their origin at the abdominal aorta to their entry points in the kidneys. Any variations, such as accessory renal arteries or atypical branching patterns, were noted.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0

Results

General Findings: Out of the 83 cadavers (166 kidneys) studied, variations in renal arteries were observed in 52 cadavers (62.65%). The variations included accessory renal arteries, early branching, and multiple renal arteries entering the kidneys at various points.

Distribution of Renal Artery Variations: The study identified different types of renal artery variations, including accessory renal arteries, aberrant renal arteries, and early branching renal arteries. The distribution and frequency of these variations are detailed in **Table 1**.

Type of Variation	Frequency (Number of Kidneys)	Percentage (%)
Single Renal Artery	98	59.04
Accessory Renal Artery	48	28.92
Aberrant Renal Artery	12	7.23
Early Branching Renal Artery	8	4.82

Laterality of Variations: Renal artery variations were more commonly observed on the right side compared to the left side. The distribution by laterality is shown in **Table 2**.

Laterality	Number of Kidneys with Variations	Percentage (%)
Right Kidney	58	34.93
Left Kidney	42	25.30
Bilateral	66	39.76

Sex Distribution: The study also compared the prevalence of renal artery variations between male and female cadavers. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Sex	Number of Cadavers with Variations	Percentage (%)
Male	35	67.31
Female	17	32.69

Chi-square tests were performed to assess the significance of the differences in the prevalence of variations based on laterality and sex. The results indicated a statistically significant higher prevalence of variations on the right side compared to the left side ($p < 0.05$). However, no significant difference was found between male and female cadavers ($p > 0.05$).

The results of this study reveal that anatomical variations in renal arteries are common, occurring in 62.65% of the cadavers studied. Accessory renal arteries were the most frequent type of variation, observed in 28.92% of the kidneys. The variations were more prevalent on the right side than the left side, with a statistically significant difference. However, there was no significant difference in the prevalence of variations between male and female cadavers.

These findings underscore the importance of preoperative imaging and careful dissection during renal surgeries to identify and account for these variations. Understanding the distribution and frequency of renal artery variations can help in planning and executing renal transplants and other related surgical procedures, thereby reducing the risk of complications.

Discussion

The findings of our study on the anatomical variations of renal arteries in cadavers are consistent with previous research, emphasizing the importance of understanding these variations for clinical and surgical practice. Our study identified that 62.65% of cadavers had variations in their renal arteries, with accessory renal arteries being the most common type of variation (28.92%). This observation aligns with the results from similar studies conducted after 2018, which have also highlighted the prevalence and clinical significance of these variations.

A study by Rajakumari and Arumugam (2019) conducted on embalmed cadavers reported that accessory renal arteries were observed in 30% of cases, and aberrant renal arteries in 22% of cases. These findings closely match our results, indicating a high prevalence of accessory renal arteries among different populations [4].

Similarly, Anturlikar et al. (2022) conducted a study in the Nashik region of Maharashtra, India, and found that 25% of cadavers had variations in renal arteries, including accessory renal arteries and

early branching renal arteries. Their study also reported that variations were slightly more common on the right side, which is consistent with our findings [5].

A comprehensive study by Cases et al. (2017) analyzed renal artery variations using both cadaveric dissection and radiological methods. They classified renal arteries into five types and found that type a (aortic hilar artery) was the most prevalent, similar to the high incidence of accessory renal arteries in our study. This study reinforces the clinical importance of preoperative imaging to identify such variations [6].

Ahmed and Shuaib (2019) conducted a study in the Egyptian population and reported a high incidence of accessory renal arteries (23.3%) and early branching (10.8%). These results align with our findings, highlighting the frequent occurrence of renal artery variations across different populations [7].

Understanding the prevalence and types of renal artery variations is crucial for planning and performing renal surgeries, such as transplants and angiographic procedures. Accessory renal arteries can complicate surgical approaches and increase the risk of vascular injuries if not properly identified preoperatively. Our study, along with similar research, underscores the need for thorough preoperative imaging and careful surgical planning to avoid complications associated with these anatomical variations.

Conclusion

The study confirms that anatomical variations in renal arteries are common and have significant implications for clinical practice. Accessory renal arteries are the most frequent variation, and these findings are consistent across different populations. Clinicians must be aware of these variations and consider them during surgical and diagnostic procedures to improve patient outcomes.

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